

Experience of the Formation of Professional Competence of Students of IT-Specialties

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Abstract : The article describes an approach to build competence in research of Bachelor and Master, which is now an important feature of modern specialist in the field of engineering. Provides an example of methodical teaching methods with the research aspect, is including the formulation of the problem, the method of conducting experiments, analysis of the results. Implementation of methods allows the student to better consolidate their knowledge and skills at the same time to get research. Knowledge on the part of the media requires some training in the subject area and teaching methods.

Keywords : professional competence, model of it-specialties, teaching methods, educational technology, decision making

Conference Title : ICCSEA 2014 : International Conference on Computer Science, Engineering and Applications

Conference Location : Paris, France

Conference Dates : May 19-20, 2014